

INFLUENCE OF IRRIGATION METHODS ON THE BIODIVERSITY OF GEOBIONTS IN THE COTTON AGROECOSYSTEM.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20095365>

The study of the biodiversity of geobionts (organisms living in the soil and underground environment) in cotton fields is one of the most pressing areas of modern agroecology and entomology. Since the cotton agroecosystem is an artificial system constantly monitored by humans, its biological balance directly depends on the activity of the soil biota and geobionts [1]. Geobionts include insect larvae, nematodes, earthworms, some beetles, termites, and other representatives of the micro- and mesofauna. They perform important ecological functions in the formation of soil structure, the decomposition of organic matter, nutrient cycling, and the regulation of phytosanitary conditions [4]. A decrease or disruption in the diversity of these groups in cotton fields leads to a decrease in soil fertility, an increase in pest numbers, and a reduction in crop yields. In recent years, as a result of intensive agricultural technology and the widespread use of chemical pesticides and mineral fertilizers, significant changes in the geobiont population have been observed. In particular, the decline in the numbers of some beneficial entomofauna disrupts the ecological balance. Therefore, assessing the biodiversity of geobionts in cotton agrobiocenoses, determining their role as ecological indicators, and developing a monitoring system are of great scientific and practical importance [6]. Furthermore, studying the composition of geobionts allows us to draw important conclusions about the biological activity of the soil, its salinity level, moisture regime, and organic matter content. This, in turn, allows for the effective organization of an integrated plant protection system (IPM) [2]. For example, some predatory beetles and parasitic nematodes play an important role in reducing pest numbers as natural biological control agents. Studying the biodiversity of geobionts in cotton fields is a strategic scientific direction not only for ensuring environmental stability but also for maintaining the long-term productivity of the agroecosystem. Therefore, the development of comprehensive monitoring, molecular analysis, and agroecological modeling in this area remains a pressing task.

Research methods. The experiment is usually conducted on three variants of cotton fields: drip irrigation under film, drip irrigation, and conventional irrigation. Each variant is organized based on a randomized block design (RBD) or a repeated-measure experiment within variants. This method allows for a scientific comparison of the effects between irrigation systems[3]. Soil samples

for determining geobionts: a square frame (square method, for example, 25x25 cm or 50x50 cm), taken from different depths (usually 0–10, 10–20, 20–30 cm). Soil traps are installed[5]. The Tullgren apparatus (separation of arthropods by light and heat gradient), the Berlese-Tullgren method, and the Berman method for nematodes are used. Isolated organisms are identified to the order, family, tribe, genus and species levels based on microscopic analysis, morphological identification keys and entomological catalogues[7].

Research results and analysis. Diagram 1 shows the distribution of geobiont biodiversity by taxonomic level under three different irrigation methods (drip irrigation under film, drip irrigation, and conventional irrigation) used in a cotton agroecosystem. The data demonstrate changes in biodiversity at the order, family, tribe, genus, and species levels, allowing for a scientific assessment of the impact of agroecological factors on soil biota.

The greatest diversity of geobionts was observed under drip irrigation (1-diagram). Three orders, six families, 13 tribes, 13 genera, and 16 species were recorded in this system. This result is explained by stable moisture retention under film, a relatively mild microclimate, and improved soil physicochemical properties. These conditions increase habitat stability for geobionts and expand their ecological niches.

Drip irrigation exhibits somewhat lower biodiversity: 3 orders, 5 families, 10 tribes, 10 genera, and 11 species. This system is also considered environmentally efficient, as it delivers water economically and maintains optimal soil moisture levels. However, the somewhat more open conditions compared to the microclimate under film may limit the growth of some types of geobionts.

1-diagram

Changes in biodiversity of geobionts in different irrigated cotton fields

In the traditional irrigation system, biodiversity has the lowest index: 2 orders, 4 families, 5 tribes, 5 genera, and 5 species. This is primarily due to uneven water distribution, frequent soil drying and wetting, and high anthropogenic pressure. These conditions destabilize the habitat of geobionts and increase environmental stress, resulting in the survival of only species with adaptive and broad ecological valence.

Overall, the results of the diagram indicate that irrigation method is one of the important agroecological factors determining the biodiversity of geobionts. In particular, drip irrigation and drip irrigation systems under film are more effective than traditional irrigation in maintaining and increasing the taxonomic diversity of soil biota.

The results of the scientific analysis also indicate that geobionts play an important role in assessing the ecological state of the soil as bioindicators. Therefore, in the future, when improving irrigation technologies, not only productivity but also the preservation of soil biodiversity should be taken into account as the main criterion.

References:

1. Begon M., Townsend C.R., Harper J.L. Ecology: From Individuals to Ecosystems. – Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, 2006. – 738 p.
2. Wall D.H., Bardgett R.D., Kelly E. Biodiversity in Agricultural Soils. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012. – 410 p.
3. Gurr G.M., Wratten S.D., Snyder W.E. Biodiversity and Insect Pests: Key Issues for Sustainable Management. – Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2012. – 287 p.

4. Kremen C., Miles A. Ecosystem services in biologically diversified versus conventional farming systems // *Ecology and Society*. – 2012. – Vol. 17(4). – P. 40–55.
5. Brown G.G. et al. Soil biodiversity and agriculture: impacts and management // *Applied Soil Ecology*. – 2015. – Vol. 88. – P. 1–9.
6. Zhang H., et al. Effects of irrigation practices on soil arthropod diversity in cotton fields // *Journal of Arid Environments*. – 2018. – Vol. 150. – P. 45–53..

